

**Synthesis and Biological Activity of
New Insecticides, Part I***

**Synthesis of N-(2-Mercapto acetyl-5-aryl-
amino, 1,3,4 Thiadiazolyl) Ureas and N'-(S-
acetyl-N-aryl Dithiocarbamoyl)-N³-Aryl Ureas**

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TWENTY new urea derivatives have been synthes-
ized by the condensation of chloroacetyl urea with
several 2-mercapto-5-aryl-amino-1,3,4 thiadiazole
and sodium salt of N-aryl dithiocarbamate. All the
compounds were tested for their insecticidal activity.

The chemistry and wide range of pesticidal¹⁻²
properties of urea derivatives have been cited in the
literature. A number of thiadiazole compounds
were reported as insecticides³, fungicides⁴ and
bactericides. The insecticidal properties of conden-
sation products of chloroacetyl urea with sodium
salt of N-aryl-dithiocarbamate were reported⁵. With
a view to study the insecticidal activity we synthesi-
zed several compounds by condensing chloroacetyl
urea, with several 2-mercapto 5-aryl-amino-1, 3, 4
thiadiazoles and sodium salt of N-aryl dithio-
carbamic acids.

In all twenty compounds have been synthesized
by replacing the active hydrogen of I and II by
chloroacetyl urea.

(I)

(II)

Experimental

Chloroacetyl urea was prepared according to the
method of Hoegberg *et al*⁶. Chloroacetyl ureas
were prepared by following the method of Jacobs
*et al*⁷. 2-Mercapto-5-aryl-amino-1, 3, 4 thiadiazoles
have been synthesized by reported methods⁸⁻⁹.
Sodium salt of N-aryl dithiocarbamic acid was
prepared by usual methods.

**N-(2-Mercapto acetyl-5-aryl-amino-1, 3, 4 thia-
diazolyl) Urea :**

A mixture of corresponding 2-mercapto-5-aryl-
amino thiadiazole (0.01 mole) and chloroacetyl urea
(0.01 mole) was refluxed in methanol for three hours
under stirring in the presence of sodium hydroxide
(0.01 mole). The reaction mixture was filtered,

solvent removed under reduced pressure and solid
obtained was recrystallised from ethanol. The
analysis and m.p.s are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield	Molecular formula	% of N	
					Found	Calc.
1.	H	210	61	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂	22.46	22.65
2.	2-CH ₃	208	60	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂	21.78	21.36
3.	3-CH ₃	199	62	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂	21.12	21.36
4.	4-CH ₃	210	68	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂	21.34	21.36
5.	2-OCH ₃	190	68	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂	21.00	20.64
6.	4-OCH ₃	197	66	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂	20.98	20.64
7.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	215	70	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂	19.46	19.83
8.	3-Chloro	203	64	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl	20.62	20.40
9.	4-Chloro	235	69	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl	20.58	20.40

N¹-(S-acetyl-N-aryl dithiocarbamoyl)-N³-aryl urea :

A mixture of the corresponding chloroacetyl aryl
urea (0.01 mole) and sodium salt of N-aryl dithio-
carbamic acid (0.01 mole) in dry acetone was reflux-
ed for two hours under stirring. The reaction
mixture was filtered and the solvent was removed
under reduced pressure. Solid obtained was
recrystallised from ethyl alcohol/acetone. M.p.s.
and analytical data are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	R ¹	R ²	M.P. °C	Yield	Molecular formula	% of N	
						Found	Calc.
10.	H	4-Br	134-35	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Br	9.78	9.90
11.	2-CH ₃	3-Cl	140-41	67	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl	10.98	10.66
12.	2-CH ₃	4-Br	180	83	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Br	9.39	9.58
13.	3-CH ₃	3-Cl	145-47	73	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl	10.91	10.66
14.	4-CH ₃	3-Cl	152	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl	10.95	10.66
15.	2-OCH ₃	3-Cl	118	78	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Cl	9.95	10.24
16.	2-OCH ₃	4-Br	131	64	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Br	9.42	9.25
17.	4-OCH ₃	3-Cl	133	81	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Cl	9.95	10.24
18.	4-OCH ₃	4-Br	135	67	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Br	9.41	9.25
19.	4-Cl	3-Cl	135	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl ₂	10.40	10.12
20.	4-Cl	4-Br	140	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ ClBr	8.89	9.15

All the melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and
are uncorrected.

Determination of Insecticidal Activity :

The method of Joshi *et al*¹⁰ was used to deter-
mine the insecticidal activity against adult male and
female cockroaches (*Periplaneta americana*). Com-
pounds were dissolved in acetone and used at a
conc. of 0.1% and 0.5%. The activity of the com-
pounds were compared with well known insecticide.

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ethyl parathion. In a concentration of 0.1% and 0.5% the mean K. D. (knock down) Time (h) of ethyl parathion is 4.5 and 5.5 respectively. All the compounds were tested but the compounds No. 8, 10, 12, 17, 19 and 20 exhibited appreciable insecticidal activity.

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Preparation and Fungitoxicity of Substituted Sulphamidophenyl-O-Alkyl Xanthates

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THIRTY two substituted sulphamidophenyl-O-alkyl xanthates have been prepared and evaluated *in vitro* against *Alternaria tenuis* and *Helminthosporium sativum*. A relation between fungitoxicity and structure has also been established.

A large number of salt of O-alkyl derivatives of xanthates have been reported in recent years to possess fungicidal activity against conidia of *M. fructicola*^{1,2}. The potassium xanthates up to C₈

were tested for toxicity in mice and Tubifex-tubifex worm³. They have also been used in the concentration of ores⁴ and cosmetics⁵. A perusal of literature on xanthates revealed that mostly they have been used as metallic salts with very little emphasis on the esters. Benzyl butyl xanthate is used as an insecticide for red spider⁶. Earlier some halogeno-nitrophenyl esters of -O-methyl and -O-ethyl xanthates were found to be toxic⁷.

This paper deals with the synthesis of substituted sulphamidophenyl-O-alkyl xanthates with efficacy results and structure-activity relationship. They have been prepared by the condensation of potassium salt of -O-alkyl xanthate(I) and diazotised sulphanilamide(II) in aqueous solution at 0-15°. The intermediate diazo derivative(III) loses nitrogen and is converted into the corresponding substituted sulphamidophenyl-O-alkyl xanthate(IV).

Experimental

Potassium salt of -O-alkyl xanthate: Prepared according to the method given in the literature⁸.

O-alkyl-substituted Sulphamidophenyl Xanthate: Substituted sulphanilamide (0.01M) dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 ml) was diluted with water (40 ml). The resulting solution was cooled to 0° and treated with a solution of sodium nitrite (0.01M) dissolved in water (10 ml). The solution of diazonium salt of sulphanilamide so obtained was then added dropwise to a well cooled solution of potassium-O-alkyl xanthate (0.01 M). The stirring was continued for half an hour. The solution was then heated on a water bath till the evolution of nitrogen ceased. On cooling, substituted sulphamidophenyl-O-alkyl xanthates separated out. These were filtered and crystallised from methyl alcohol. The physical data of these compounds are given in Table 1 alongwith their fungitoxicity.

Fungitoxicity of substituted sulphamidophenyl-O-alkyl xanthates:

These compounds were tested for their anti-fungal activity against *Alternaria tenuis* and *Helminthosporium sativum* by spore germination method⁹. Ed₅₀ values were determined from data for five con-

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